

SYSTEM SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF GENERAL SECONDARY EDUCATION PROCESSES

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Annotation: The article provides information on independent education, self-education, independent work, as well as system-specific features of education and training processes, which are organized by students themselves in general secondary education schools.

Key words: traditional lecture, seminar, practical training, group training, excursion, round discussion, meetings, pedagogical experience-testing and pedagogical practice processes, education, upbringing, independent education, self-education.

Distance education (online, offline) organized in general secondary schools and competitions, contests, art festivals, conferences and events organized by subjects, independent education, self-education, independent information, independent works, as well as educational activities carried out by students themselves. the process of relations and the processes of pedagogical experience-testing and pedagogical practice constitute the system of education and training processes organized in UOM.

That is, the efficiency of distance education (online, offline) has a direct impact on the efficiency of a number of other education, upbringing, independent education, self-education and educational relations processes.

Therefore, based on the characteristics of the system of education and training processes, it shows the importance of taking into account the effectiveness of education and training processes not only in general schools, but also in non-school educational institutions, and confirms it as a necessity.

Therefore, the system specific features of general secondary education processes become important when the educational process organized for a specific

purpose serves for a common goal or vice versa, that is, the educational process organized in the direction of a common goal serves for all components of a common goal. That is, to see its importance in the fact that the processes of imparting knowledge to students serve to direct them to a profession, teach and develop creative thinking, as well as to form the skills of a conscious attitude to the environment, the correct choice of the next educational path, and the formation of the skills of choosing a profession in accordance with their needs, interests and abilities. possible

Also, the introduction of primary education (grades I-IV) as a constituent component of general secondary education, which is one of the components of the continuing education system, in regulatory documents shows that general secondary education is also considered a system with its constituent components. That is, the inclusion of primary education (grades I-IV) as a component of the type of general secondary education is the basis for saying that general secondary education is a sub-system within the continuous education system.

One of the principles of the organization and development of continuous education is the interdependence of education and upbringing, the principle that this process is oriented towards the formation of a person who has matured in all respects. implies organization in integral connection with, that is, organization and management of general secondary education processes on the basis of systematic approaches. This, in turn, confirms that general secondary education processes have system-specific features.

The fact that general secondary education is a system consisting of several components, and ensuring the interdependence of these components, that it has system-specific features, also represents the following tasks assigned to general secondary education:

ensuring regular knowledge acquisition by students, developing their need for learning, forming basic educational, scientific and general cultural knowledge;

formation of students' work skills, creative independent thinking, conscious attitude to the choice of profession and the environment;

on the basis of integral integration of national and universal values, education of high spiritual and moral qualities in students, formation of a citizen loyal to his Motherland and people;

to ensure the continuity and consistency of education, the seamless interconnection of school curricula with academic lyceums and vocational colleges.

According to the established procedure, the content of general secondary education should consist of mandatory and additional components, it is necessary that the mandatory component is determined by the state educational standard, and it is necessary to determine the more thorough study of the basics of knowledge and the acquisition of a profession in secondary special and vocational educational institutions, and it is important that the additional component is determined based on the needs and abilities of the student, the material and technical base of the school and the provision of personnel is considered.

Therefore, the educational processes organized at both stages of general secondary education, which is one of the main types of continuous education system, are distance learning (online, offline), theoretical, practical and laboratory exercises, which are considered traditional classes, circle exercises, round discussions, which are considered extracurricular activities, meetings, intellectual-creative events, Olympiads of sciences, sports competitions and contests, art festivals, science nights, and excursions and spiritual-educational activities, which are considered extracurricular activities, include the processes of independent education and educational relations. These educational processes also have system-specific features, and the need to ensure their interdependence and connection is the basis for describing general secondary education processes as a whole system.

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